

THERAPEUTIC EFFICACY OF PRACCHANA IN KHALITYA: A POST-PROCEDURE APPLICATION OF TRIPHALA MASI

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ABSTRACT

Alopecia is caused by androgen and genetic factors. Androgens cause hair follicles to shrink and eventually disappear if they are not addressed. A 40- year-old male presented to the Shalyatantra OPD Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya Hubballi, with complaints of gradual hair loss and scalp itching over a two-year period. It was diagnosed as a case of Khalitya and was treated with Pracchana and Masi application. The Norman Hamilton scale, hair pull test and symptoms before and after treatment were used to evaluate the case. Following treatment, there was a significant reduction in symptoms and significant hair growth.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Khalitya, Pracchana, Masi, Case Report.

INTRODUCTION

Hair has been traditionally associated with beauty and grandeur. Long, thick hair has been a symbol of attractiveness, and it has a significant impact on the cosmetic industry in civilized nations. In this era where grooming and appearances are vital, hair loss can highly distressful and may impact on the quality of life of an individual. The overall incidence of Alopecia is approximately 20.2 per 100,000 people. The prevalence of Alopecia ranges from 0.1 to 0.2%, depending on the geographic location and ethnic background. Alopecia incidence appears to increase almost linearly with age, but the mean age of onset appears to be between 25 and 36

years. Androgenic alopecia affects about 60% of men, throughout their lives, and probably 25% of women.^[1] Alopecia may be associated with hyperthyroidism, psoriasis, stress, inflammatory bowel disease. The active phase, also known as the anagen phase, is the first of three stages in the hair cycle. The hair develops and replaces the old hair during this period, and it continues to grow for several weeks to a few years. Catagen is the second phase, which is the transition from active to resting hair and can take up to three weeks. Telogen is the third stage of hair growth in which hair remains in the scalp without developing and can be removed by pulling and combing the hair. Also, the hair may remain at this stage until the new hair grows and naturally pulls the old hair out and this phase might last up to three months. Acharya Charaka classified Khalitya under Shiroroga and Acharya Vagbhata considered it under Kapalagata Roga,^[2] while Acharya Sushruta,^[3] Vrudda Vagbhata,^[4] Yoga Ratnakara and Madhavakara, has included Khalitya disease under Kshudra Roga. Which is due to mildness of the disease.^[5] Treatment of Khalitya is Raktamokshana, it is the only Shodhana procedure where the vitiated Doshas are taken out from the Shakhas itself by creating an artificial route. Pracchana is one among the Shastrakrita Raktamokshana in which multiple small incisions are made in wide area to irrigate the impure blood.^[6]

CASE REPORT

Patient information A 40-year-old male patient presented to the Outpatient Department of Shalyatantra, Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya college and hospital Hubballi, with complaints of hair loss and itching on the scalp for the past three years. Clinical findings the patient was asymptomatic for three years before experiencing gradual hair loss and scalp irritation. Before three years, there was an episode of hair donation and following that, he noticed patchy hair loss. It was first noticed on the parietal part of the scalp and subsequently progressed day by day. These patches were approximately 2-3cm in size. It had spread throughout the entire scalp within three months. He has been on contemporary treatment for two years and has seen no progress. So, he approached, Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya college and hospital, Hubballi for improved management. First degree relatives had no family history of this condition. There had been no history of known endocrinological abnormalities. Dashavidha Pariksha The patients Prakriti (~body constitution) was Pitta Vataja, whereas the Vikriti (~ abnormal body constitutions) was Tridoshaja, Satva (~will power) was Avara, Samhanana (~compactness), Sara (~essence of tissues), Satyma (~homologation), Ahara Shakti (~ability to assimilate food), Vyayama Shakti (~ability to perform strenuous work), Vaya (~age) and Bala (~strength) was Madhyama.

Table 1: Treatment Timeline.

Sitting	Day	Procedure	Description
01	Day 1	Prachanna ^[7] karma+Triphala masi ^[8]	Controlled pricking over affected scalp. Immediate application of Triphala Masi
02	Day 8	Prachanna karma+Triphala masi	Repeat prachanna at healing margins Reapply Triphala Masi to stimulate follicles
03	Day 15	Prachanna karma+Triphala masi	Focus on areas with persistent Kleda or hair thinning Triphala Masi for Rasayana effect
04	Day 22	Prachanna karma+Triphala masi	Assess scalp texture and regrowth Reapply with gentle massage
05	Day 29	Prachanna karma+Triphala masi	Target dormant follicles Optional mild Swedana before application
06	Day 36	Prachanna karma+Triphala masi	Evaluate hair density and scalp tone Reapply Triphala Masi
07	Day 43	Prachanna karma+Triphala masi	Final sitting Document therapeutic outcome and plan follow- up

Table 2: Medications that are prescribed during discharge.

Medication	Dosage
Bhringaraj taila ^[9]	Massage to scalp thrice weekly
Gandhaka rasayana ^[10]	500mg BD after food
Laghusutasekara rasa ^[11]	500mg BD Before food
Arogyavardhini vati ^[12]	500mg BD after food

Assessment Criteria

Table 3: Keshabhumi.

No hairfall	Grade 0
Hairfall once while washing hairs	Grade 1
Hairfall on combing	Grade 2
Hairfall even without combing and raised hairline in frontal region	Grade 3

Table 4: Darunaka.

Absent	Grade 0
Mild	Grade 1
Moderate	Grade 2
Severe	Grade 3

Table 5: Kesha Bhumi Rukshata.

Smooth hair surface	Grade 0
Occasional rough hair surface	Grade 1
Slight rough hair surface	Grade 2
Rough hair surface	Grade 3

Table 6: Kesha bhumi kandu.

Absent	Grade 0
Mild itching	Grade 1
Moderate itching	Grade 2
Severe itching	Grade 3

Table 7: Pull Test.

0-10	Grade 0
11-15	Grade 1
16-20	Grade 2
Above 20	Grade 3

Table 8: For Male Pattern Baldness: The Modified Norwood – Hamilton Scale.

SN	Stages	Grading
1	Full head of hair without any hair fall	0
2	Minor recession at the front of the hairline	1
3	Further loss at the front of the hairline which is considered "cosmetically significant"	2
4	Progressively more loss along the front hairline and at the crown	3
5	Hair loss extends toward the vertex	4
6	Frontal and vertex balding areas merge into one and increase in size	5
7	The last stage of male-pattern baldness in which all hair is lost along the front hairline	6

Table 9: Outcome.

SN	Symptoms	Before treatment (1 st day)	After treatment (43 rd day)
1	Kesha shatana	3	1
2	Kesha Bhoomi rukshata	3	2
3	Kesha Bhoomi kandu	2	1
4	Darunaka	0	0
5	Hair pull test	3	1
6	The modified Norwood-hamilton scale	4	3

DISCUSSION

Khalitya is Pitta Pradhana Tridoshajanya Vyadhi along with Rakta. Vitiated Bhrajaka Pitta along with vitiating Vata leads to weakening of the hair from the hair roots. Vitiating Kapha along with Rakta obstructs the hair roots which prevent further hair growth.^[13] Pracchana Karma enables the damaged hair follicles to recover through their inherent regenerative capacity. It relieves the blockage at the root of hairs, “Pracchane Pinditehitam” & stimulates scalp metabolism by increasing blood circulation.^[14] Pracchana increases the circulation in the scalp. It removes the vitiating Rakta and Kapha which obstructs the hair roots.^[15] Pracchana improves the perifollicular vascularisation and strengthens the hair follicle. In the context of Pracchana Karma, classical formulations like Bhringaraj Taila, Gandhaka Rasayana, Laghu Sutashekhara Rasa, Arogyavardhini Vati, and Triphala Masi play a synergistic role in enhancing therapeutic outcomes. Bhringaraj Taila supports follicular regeneration post-procedure, while Gandhaka Rasayana boosts tissue immunity and healing. Laghu Sutashekhara Rasa pacifies Pitta-related imbalances often linked to Khalitya, and Arogyavardhini Vati aids systemic detoxification, especially in Rakta and Yakrit disorders. Triphala Masi, with its Ropana and Shodhana properties, serves as an ideal wound dressing, promoting clean and swift healing of the micro-channels created during Pracchana.^[16,17,18]

CONCLUSION

In this generation, poor lifestyle choices have made a substantial contribution to premature hair loss. People have turned to Ayurveda because of the failure of conventional techniques. The success of this case demonstrates how Ayurveda may perform work wonders in cases of Khalitya.

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